

Evaluation of Histopathological changes in Gastroesophageal Reflux

Disease by using a modified Los Angeles scoring system

Sundarapandiyan Sundaramoorthy¹, Vijaya Kumar Kumaresan^{2***},
Ambedkar Raj Kulandaivelu³, Sasianand Duraimanickam⁴

1. Assistant professor, Department of Pathology, Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research centre, Trichy.
2. Post-graduate, Department of Pathology, Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research centre, Trichy.
3. Professor, Department of Pathology, Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research centre, Trichy.
4. Professor, Department of Gastroenterology, Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research centre, Trichy.

Running title: HPE in GERD by modified LA scoring.

***Corresponding Author:

Vijayakumar Kumaresan

Postgraduate Student

Department of Pathology

Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research centre, Irungalur, Trichy- 621105

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Abstract

Back ground: Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease (GERD) is ever increasing burden globally and many with GERD show normal studies on endoscopy. A histological examination might provide a definite diagnosis.

Objectives: To study the spectrum of histopathological changes in patients presenting with GERD symptoms and to quantify the histopathological changes associated with GERD using the Modified Los Angeles Scoring System.

Material and Methods: The present study had a cross-sectional study design (Data retrieved from the records) and was carried out in the Department of Pathology, Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre for 2 months. The study participants were all those aged more than 18 years who had undergone endoscopic guided upper Gastrointestinal biopsy for the symptoms of GERD. The biopsies were analysed histomorphometrically and the findings were recorded.

Results: 42 (76,4%) had basal cell hyperplasia of more than 25%. 47 (85.5%) had papillae elongation of more than 66%. With regard to the presence of intraepithelial T lymphocytes, 37 (67.3%) had more than 10 cells per high-power field. 5(9.1%) were found to have gastric metaplasia and 3 (5.5%) had intestinal metaplasia. 18 (32.7%) had a histological score of 6, 15 (27.3%) had a score of 5, and 11(20%) had a score of 7. 5(9.1%) had a score of 8 and 2 (3.6%) had a score of 9.

Conclusion: Histological changes in GERD can be permanent and can aid in the diagnosis of GERD even in superficial biopsies.

Key words: GERD, hyperplasia, intraepithelial T lymphocytes, metaplasia, papillae elongation.

Introduction

Gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) is a chronic symptom due to the involuntary passage of acid present in the stomach into the oesophagus leading to mucosal damage. GERD is otherwise called acid reflux disease or gastric reflux disease¹. The burden of GERD is ever increasing globally. Factors like ageing global population and the ongoing epidemic of obesity were linked to the increasing trend².

The reflex can be end result of either a reduced lower oesophageal sphincter tone or due to enhanced pressure in the abdomen. Substance abuse like using tobacco and alcohol, being obese and being pregnant are all factors that can increase the probability of GERD. The sufferers can experience complications due to chronic nature of the condition and these varies from inflammation, fibrosis to adenocarcinoma³.

The diagnosis of GERD is usually done based in the symptoms and how is responds to the administration of proton pump inhibitors(PPI)^{4,5}. If not responding the next line of investigation will be an endoscopy. Based on endoscopic findings, the GERD can be either erosive or non-erosive. For many the endoscopy reveals a normal study. In such cases, only doing a histological examination will reveal the evidence of GERD⁶. The histological changes^{6,7} indicating GERD include the evidence for oedema, hyperplasia of the basal cells, papillae elongation, lymphocytic inflammation, squamous cell layer may show thinning and there can be intestinal or gastric metaplasia⁷.

Hence, even those with normal finding in endoscopy, a histological examination may lead to definite diagnosis of GERD. The present study was carried out to study the spectrum of histopathological changes in patients presenting with GERD symptoms and to quantify the histopathological changes associated with GERD using the Modified Los Angeles Scoring System.

Material and Methods

The present study had a cross-sectional study design and was carried out in the department of Pathology, Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre. The consent for the study was obtained from the institutional ethics committee. The study participants were all those age more than 18 years who had undergone endoscopic guided upper GI biopsy for the symptoms of GERD. The study was carried out for a period of 2 months between May 2025 to June 2025.

The sample size for the study was estimated as 55. Those with history of PPI in the last four weeks, any history of oesophageal surgery or major upper GI resection, non-representative biopsy samples, inadequate or insufficient biopsy samples and biopsy samples that had undergone severe autolysis were excluded. The data for the study was collected using a pretested proforma.

Data for the study was collected from secondary sources. The data collected include age of the study participant and the gender. The symptom of GERD as reported by the participant at the time of admission was noted down. Details regarding smoking and alcohol consumption for each participant was recorded. The dietary habit was recorded as vegetarian or mixed diet along with preferred characteristic like spiciness of the food and fatty food. The frequency of caffeine intake per day was noted down. The use of Non-Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDS) were sought for and recorded. The biopsies were then analysed histologically. The sections that were properly oriented with adequate staining were included. The reflex related changes were observed. These include the presence of hyperplasia of the basal cells, papillae elongation, gastric or intestinal metaplasia and presence of intraepithelial lymphocytes⁸. The intraepithelial cells were then examined in 5 High Power Field (HPF) and the nuclear contour was studied for any irregularity. The average number of such cells per HPF was then calculated and recorded. In order to confirm the nature of the irregular nuclear contour, immunohistochemical staining was performed using anti-CD3 monoclonal antibody. The sub-epithelial zone was examined and the presence of any neutrophils, lymphocytes, eosinophils and fibrosis was documented.

Leitz optical micrometre was used to do the morphometric assessment. The following parameters including the total thickness of the squamous epithelium, basal cell thickness and elongation of stromal papilla were documented from five well oriented areas. Their average values were then calculated. Based on the

findings the grade was identified using Los Angeles Classification system. Table 1 shows the grading of Los Angeles Classification system.

The data collected were entered into Microsoft excel 2019 and the master chart was created. The variables were described using frequency and percentages. Bar charts were used to depict certain data diagrammatically.

Results

Among the participants included into the study, 25 (45.5) were of age 41 to 60 years and 18 (32.7%) of age 18 to 40 years. 34 (61.8%) were males. 55 (100%) reported heart burn, 41 (74.5%) reported regurgitation, 38 (69.1%) reported nausea, 23 (41.8%) complained dysphagia and 18 (32.7%) complained vomiting. 18 (32.7%) were smokers and 21 (38.2%) reported alcohol consumption. 49 (89.1%) consumed mixed diet while the rest were vegetarians. 36 (63.6%) reported to frequently consume spicy food, 21 (38.2%) consumed fatty foods frequently and 34 (61.8%) reported to consume more than 3 cups of coffee in a day. 19 (34.5%) reported frequent use of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory agents. 11(20%) had diabetes, 15 (27.3%) had hypertension and 6(10.9%) had both (Table 2).

Based on the histomorphometric examination of the biopsies, 42 (76.4%) had basal cell hyperplasia of more than 25% and 11 (20%) had basal cell hyperplasia of 15 to 25%. 47 (85.5%) had papillae elongation of more than 66% and 8(14.5%) had papillae elongation of 33 to 66%. With regard to the presence of intraepithelial T lymphocytes, 37 (67.3%) had more than 10 cells per high power field and 16 (29.1%) had 6 to 10 cells per HPF. With regard to the intraepithelial eosinophils per HPF, more than 10 cells were found in 3 (5.5%), 6 to 10 cells in 15 (27.3%) and 37 (67.3%) had 5 cells per HPF. 5(9.1%) were found to have gastric metaplasia and 3 (5.5%) had intestinal metaplasia (Table 3).

18 (32.7%) had a histological score of 6, 15 (27.3%) had a score of 5 and 11(20%) had a score of 7. 5(9.1%) had a score of 8 and 2 (3.6%) had a score of 9 (Fig 1).

Discussion

Gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) is a major public health problem and continues to do so due to its ever-increasing prevalence, incidence and Years lost to disability⁹. When the endoscopy turns out to be normal, a histological examination might reveal the presence of GERD and aid in diagnosis of the same^{6,7}. The present study was carried out to study the spectrum of histopathological changes in patients presenting with GERD symptoms and to quantify the histopathological changes associated with GERD using Modified Los Angeles Scoring System.

The male to female ratio in the present study was 2:1. Yaseri HF reported similar higher probability of oesophageal reflux disease in males than females¹⁰. Eslick GD et al reported smokers to have 2.4 times increased risk of getting GERD than the nonsmokers¹¹. In the present study about 32% reported to be smokers. Pan J et al reported 1.48 times increased risk of getting GERD for alcoholics than non or occasional drinkers¹². Blaga S et al reported caffeine intake as risk factor for GERD and so does taking in spicy foods¹³. In the present study 63% reported to consume spicy foods frequently and 61.8% consumed more than 3 cups of coffee in a day.

Most biopsies in the present study had basal cell hyperplasia of more than 25% and papillae elongation of more than 66%. The intraepithelial t lymphocytes infiltration was more than the eosinophils. 67% had histological score of 5 to 6. Dunbar KB et al reported results similar to that of the present study. The biopsies were taken 2 weeks following the discontinuation of PPI and the study documented an increase in the intraepithelial lymphocytes along with basal cell hyperplasia, papillary hyperplasia and widened intracellular spaces¹⁴. Vieth M et al reported that the one assessment that is more relevant to diagnose GERD would be papillae elongation. The study added intraepithelial lymphocytic infiltrate could indicate the severity of GERD and is more common than eosinophil or neutrophil infiltration¹⁵.

Zentilin P et al reported 96% and 76% among those with erosive and non-erosive esophagitis to have abnormal histology¹⁶. Tytgat GNJ et al that the histological changes are non-uniform and varies in circumferential and longitudinal distributions. Since the acid exposure is more superficial so will the changes stated the study. The study concluded random routine non targeted biopsies may not be useful¹⁷. Kataria J et al in their systematic review stated that biopsies taken within 3 cm from the lower oesophageal sphincter had a sensitivity of 71% and specificity of 64%¹⁸.

The strength of the present study is to document the histological changes present among those with gastroesophageal reflux disease particularly those with normal endoscopy. The study was carried out in a tertiary care centre, hence generalisability has to be done with caution.

Conclusion

Among those with normal endoscopy, GERD can be diagnosed with the histological changes and also the scoring. These changes might be permanent and with superficial biopsies alone, the diagnosis can be made. Since non erosive GERD was the commonest form, histomorphological diagnosis will play a key role in both the diagnosis and the decrease in disability among the sufferers of GERD.

Ethical clearance : All procedures performed in the current study were approved by IRB and/or national research ethics committee (691/ TSRMMCH&RC/ME-1/2025-IEC NO:187 & 08.05.2025) in accordance with the 1964 Helsinki declaration and its later amendments.

"Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study."

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Author Contribution information:

Conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, project administration, resources, writing : Sundarapandiyar Sundaramoorthy, Vijaya Kumar Kumaresan

Supervision : Ambedkar Raj Kulandaivelu³, Sasianand Duraimanickam⁴

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Tables and Figures**Table 1: Scoring scale of histological parameters.**

Histological parameter	Histological Criteria	Score
Basal cell hyperplasia	<15%	0
	15-25%	1
	>25%	2
Elongation of papillae	<33%	0
	33-66%	1
	>66%	2
Intraepithelial T lymphocytes (CINC)/HPF	5	0
	6-10	1
	>10	2
Intraepithelial Eosinophils/HPF	5	0
	6-10	1
	>10	2
Metaplasia	Gastric	2
	Intestinal	4

Table 2: Sociodemographic, behavioural risk factors and treatment history among the study participants.

Variables		Frequency (n=55)	Percentage (%)
Age group (in years)	18-40	18	32.7
	41-60	25	45.5
	>60	12	21.8
Gender	Male	34	61.8
	Female	21	38.2
Symptoms	Heart burn	55	100
	Dysphagia	23	41.8
	Regurgitation	41	74.5
	Nausea	38	69.1
	Vomiting	18	32.7
Smoking	Present	18	32.7
	Absent	37	67.3
Alcohol consumption	Present	21	38.2
	Absent	34	61.8
Type of diet	Mixed	49	89.1
	Vegetarian	6	10.9
Frequency of spicy food	Frequent	35	63.6
	Occasional	20	36.4
Frequency of fatty food	Frequent	21	38.2
	Occasional	34	61.8
Caffeine intake	>3 in a day	34	61.8
	< 3 in a day	16	29.1
	Nil	5	9.1
Frequent use of NSAID	Present	19	34.5
	Absent	36	65.5
Comorbidities	Diabetes	11	20
	Hypertension	15	27.3
	Both	6	10.9

Table 3: Distribution according to histomorphometric findings of the biopsies among the participants.

Histological parameter	Histological Criteria	Frequency (n=55)	Percentage (%)
Basal cell hyperplasia	<15%	2	3.6
	15-25%	11	20
	>25%	42	76.4
Elongation of papillae	<33%	0	0
	33-66%	8	14.5
	>66%	47	85.5
Intraepithelial T lymphocytes (CINC)/HPF	5	2	3.6
	6-10	16	29.1
	>10	37	67.3
Intraepithelial Eosinophils/HPF	5	37	67.3
	6-10	15	27.3
	>10	3	5.5
Metaplasia	Gastric	5	9.1
	Intestinal	3	5.5

Figure 1: Bar chart showing distribution according to histological score among the participants.

